

Supplementary appendix S2: GRADE assessment

Summary of findings table 1: can acupuncture plus antidepressants improve the therapeutic effectiveness in patients with depression?

Can acupuncture plus antidepressants improve the therapeutic effectiveness in patients with depression?						
Patient or population: depression Settings: community/ outpatient/ inpatient Intervention: acupuncture plus antidepressants Comparison: antidepressants						
Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Antidepressants	Acupuncture plus antidepressants				
HAMD-17 score - MA plus antidepressants		The mean hamd-17 score - ma plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 1.88 lower (2.08 to 1.69 lower)		477 (3 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ¹	
HAMD-17 score - EA plus antidepressants		The mean hamd-17 score - ea plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 2.1 lower (2.85 to 1.35 lower)		564 (5 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ²	
SDS score - EA plus antidepressants		The mean sds score - ea plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 3.58 lower (5.19 to 1.96 lower)		470 (3 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ³	

PHQ-9 score - acupuncture plus antidepressants	The mean phq-9 score - acupuncture plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 3.3 lower (4.67 to 1.93 lower)		377 (1 study)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ low ^{4,5}	
MADRS score - acupuncture plus antidepressants	The mean madrs score - acupuncture plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 6.08 lower (10.59 to 1.58 lower)		156 (2 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ very low ^{6,7,8}	
Remission rate of HAMD-17 - EA plus antidepressants	Study population		RR 1.48 (1.1 to 2)	490 (3 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ moderate ³
	210 per 1000	311 per 1000 (231 to 420)			
	Moderate				
	229 per 1000	339 per 1000 (252 to 458)			
Treatment response of HAMD-17 - EA plus antidepressants	Study population		RR 1.34 (1.14 to 1.58)	622 (5 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊕ moderate ⁹
	493 per 1000	661 per 1000 (562 to 780)			
	Moderate				
	417 per 1000	559 per 1000 (475 to 659)			

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; **RR:** Risk ratio; **MA:** Manual acupuncture; **EA:** Electro-acupuncture; **HAMD-17:** Hamilton Depression Scale-17; **SDS:** Self-rating Depression Scale; **PHQ-9:** Patient Health Questionnaire-9; **MADRS:** Montgomery and Asberg Depression Rating Scale

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High quality: Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect.

Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

Low quality: Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

Very low quality: We are very uncertain about the estimate.

¹ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of bias in the blinding of participants of all included studies.

² Downgraded one level owing to high risk of performance bias across most included studies, of five trials, three trials were at high risk of bias owing to lack of blinding of participants.

³ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of performance bias across most included studies, of three trials, two trials were at high risk of bias owing to lack of blinding of participants.

⁴ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of bias in the blinding of participants of the included study.

⁵ Downgraded one level owing to small sample size and only one study reporting on this outcome.

⁶ Downgraded two level owing to serious risk of performance bias across most included studies, of two trials, one trial was at high risk of bias owing to allocation concealment and lack of blinding of participants, another study was high risk of bias owing to selective reporting.

⁷ Downgraded two levels owing to considerable heterogeneity.

⁸ Downgraded one level owing to small sample size of all included studies.

⁹ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of performance bias across most included studies, of five trials, four trials were at high risk of bias owing to lack of blinding of participants.

Summary of findings table 2: can acupuncture plus antidepressants reduce adverse drug reactions in patients with depression?

Can acupuncture plus antidepressants reduce adverse drug reactions in patients with depression?

Patient or population: depression

Settings: community/ outpatient/ inpatient

Intervention: acupuncture plus antidepressants

Comparison: antidepressants

Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Antidepressants	Acupuncture plus antidepressants				
Number of participants who reported adverse drug reactions - MA plus antidepressants	Study population		RR 0.32 (0.12 to 0.82)	564 (4 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ¹	
	56 per 1000	18 per 1000 (7 to 46)				
	Moderate	19 per 1000 (7 to 49)				
SERS score - EA plus antidepressants	The mean sers score - ea plus antidepressants in the intervention groups was 2.38 lower (3.23 to 1.53 lower)			308 (1 study)	⊕ ⊕ ⊖ ⊖ low ^{2,3}	

*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; **RR:** Risk ratio; **MA:** Manual acupuncture; **EA:** Electro-acupuncture; **SERS:** Rating Scale for Side Effects

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High quality: Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect.

Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

Low quality: Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

Very low quality: We are very uncertain about the estimate.

¹ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of performance bias across most included studies, of four trials, two trials were at high risk of bias owing to selective reporting, and one trial was at high risk of bias owing to lack of blinding of participants.

² Downgraded one level owing to high risk of bias in the blinding of participants of the included study.

³ Downgraded one level owing to only one study reporting on this outcome.

Summary of findings table 3: can acupuncture plus antidepressants decrease number of participants who increased antidepressants dosage?

Can acupuncture plus antidepressants decrease number of participants who increased antidepressants dosage?						
Patient or population: depression						
Settings: community/ outpatient/ inpatient						
Intervention: acupuncture plus antidepressants						
Comparison: antidepressants						
Outcomes	Illustrative comparative risks* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of Participants (studies)	Quality of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Assumed risk	Corresponding risk				
	Antidepressants	Acupuncture plus antidepressants				
Number of participants who increased antidepressants dosage subgroup - MA plus antidepressants	Study population		RR 0.21 (0.11 to 0.41)	413 (2 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ¹	
	222 per 1000	47 per 1000 (24 to 91)				
	Moderate					
Number of participants who increased antidepressants dosage subgroup - EA plus antidepressants	Study population		RR 0.43 (0.26 to 0.71)	412 (2 studies)	⊕ ⊕ ⊕ ⊖ moderate ¹	
	222 per 1000	95 per 1000 (58 to 157)				
	Moderate					

	224 per 1000	96 per 1000 (58 to 159)	
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*The basis for the **assumed risk** (e.g. the median control group risk across studies) is provided in footnotes. The **corresponding risk** (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; **RR:** Risk ratio; **MA:** Manual acupuncture; **EA:** Electro-acupuncture

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High quality: Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect.

Moderate quality: Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

Low quality: Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

Very low quality: We are very uncertain about the estimate.

¹ Downgraded one level owing to high risk of bias in the blinding of participants of all included studies.
